

Design, assembly and operation of a Cosmic Ray Tagger based on scintillators and SiPMs

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Abstract

The Mu2e experiment at Fermilab aims to search for the SM forbidden $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ conversion in Al muonic atoms. The signal signature consists of 104.96 MeV electrons, identified by a straw-tube tracker and a crystal calorimeter, made of two annular disks. In order to calibrate the calorimeter disks with minimum ionizing particles (MIP) before the installation, we have realized a Cosmic Ray Tagger (CRT) at Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati (LNF) of INFN. The CRT consists of two planes of eight $2.5 \times 1.5 \times 160$ cm³ plastic scintillator (EJ-200) bars, coupled to SiPMs on both edges, so as to estimate longitudinal hit positions from time differences. 3D MIP tracking is achieved by reconstructing hit positions in the two planes, placed above and below the disks, and allows to calibrate the energy response, to align the time offsets, and to study the detector performances dependence along the crystals axis.

1. Introduction

The Mu2e experiment at Fermilab will search for the Charged Lepton Flavour Violating (CLFV) process of coherent μ^- to e^- conversion in the Coulomb field of Al nuclei. The experimental goal is to improve the current limit on conversion by four orders of magnitude, reaching a single-event sensitivity less than $3 \cdot 10^{-17}$. With this aim, an intense pulsed low-momentum beam is produced and transported to an Al stopping target. The conversion signature is a 104.96 MeV monoenergetic electron, identified by straw-tube tracker and an electromagnetic calorimeter. In particular, the calorimeter is composed of two annular disks with a total of 1378 undoped CsI crystals, each one coupled to two custom UV-extended Mu2e-SiPMs, and will withstand a 10^{-4} Torr vacuum, 1 T B-field, in a very harsh radiation environment [1] [2]. Prior to the installation in the final hall, the two calorimeter disks will be scanned with cosmic rays, so as to calibrate energy response and to align time offsets of all calorimeter channels. With this aim a Cosmic Ray Tagger (CRT) - with 3D tracking capabilities - has been realized. The CRT will also allow to study the dependence of energy and timing resolution along the crystals z-axis.

2. Cosmic Ray Tagger

The CRT consists of two planar modules, each one composed of a 8 parallel $2.5 \times 1.5 \times 160$ cm³ EJ-200 scintillating bars, with a dual-side readout based on custom UV-extended

large area SiPMs, coupled through optical grease.

The EJ-200 scintillator material is a doped polyvinyltoluene polymer, showing high light output ($\sim 10^4$ photons/MeV, peaked at 425 nm), a large bulk attenuation length (BAL) of 380 cm (well suited for the 160 cm bar length along the longitudinal axis Z) and a fast rise time (900 ps). The bars were wrapped with 150 μ m Tyvek foil and an outer 500 μ m Mylar layer and darkened with black tape.

With a gain of 3.6×10^6 , a MIP peak is visible at a ~ 480 pC charge (after SiPM V_{bias} adjustments to equalize the channels with a 6% maximum spread), for hits at center of the bars, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Charge histogram fitted with a Landau distribution, for cosmic rays selected with a 10 cm wide scintillator at the bar center.

The timing of each SiPM is reconstructed using a template fit procedure, in order to evaluate time differences ΔT between the two sides. The single-readout time resolution $\sigma_{\Delta T} / \sqrt{2}$ was evaluated and fitted with a three-component model, for both β

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(from a collimated source) and cosmic rays (selected using two 1cm wide scintillators), as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Time resolution vs. charge.

The longitudinal position (Z) is reconstructed from ΔT using the effective light speed in the bars $v_p = (14.33 \pm 0.05)$ cm/ns, evaluated by scanning a bar with a β source and fitting the ΔT vs. Z graph with a linear function, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 3: ΔT vs. Z .

This reconstruction technique has been tested by triggering on the coincidence of both modules, placed one on top on the other at a $\Delta Y = 10$ cm vertical distance. The resulting hit profile along Z is flat with gaussian tails, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Z histogram, fitted with a convolution of a Gaussian and a uniform distribution.

Reconstructing Z allows also to easily estimate the light attenuation along the bar axis, modelled as a double exponential function (for direct and indirect light), in agreement with the nominal BAL and technical attenuation lengths (TAL) from 30

to 70 cm, with a maximum attenuation factor of 26%, as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Most probable values of Landau distributions fitted from MIP charge histograms, for different Z slices.

Using the described technique, the CRT apparatus allows to track muons in 3D, by reconstructing the hit position in the two planes (placed above and below the disks), both on the transversal direction using the $2.5\text{mm} \times 8$ segmentation and on the Z axis (with a σ_Z of 1.6 cm at the center and 2.3 cm at the edges). The CRT has been completely assembled and characterized, showing good performances and 3D tracking capabilities. It is now going to be tested along with a large scale prototype of the calorimeter, in order to validate the calibration procedures.

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